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STUDY ON HUMAN CORNEAL ULCERS IN TANTA UNIVERSITY OPHTHALMOLOGY HOSPITALS WITH SPECIAL ATTENTION TO MYCOTIC KERATITIS.

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Fungal keratitis was diagnosed in 74 out of 991 patients presented to Ophthalmology Clinic of Tanta University Hospital with corneal ulcers of different types during the period from May 2000 to April 2002. The clinical and biological aspects of these cases were described. Noteworthy was the first known human fungal keratitis cases caused by *Trimmatostroma salicis*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Stachybotrys chartarum* and *Mortierella horticola*. Studies on patients with fungal corneal ulcers showed that the most common fungi were *Aspergillus flavus*, *Mucor racemosus*, *Penicillium lanosum* and *Aspergillus niger*. It was observed that fungal corneal ulcers were common among males more than females, over the age of 40, among farmers, housewives and rural residence more than indoor workers with urban residence. Therefore, the importance of the eye protection, hygiene education, and improving medical care to reduce the occurrence of fungal corneal ulcers must be emphasized. Activities of some enzymes (collagenase, phospholipase, protease, urease, and catalase) were tested for all isolated fungi.

Key words: Fungal keratitis, collagenase, phospholipase, protease, urease and catalase.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal keratitis was considered one of the major causes of infectious keratitis in tropical areas. The severity of mycotic keratitis is due to misdiagnosis, absence of a definite shape for infected lesion, absence of topical antifungal agents prepared for ocular use, nephrotoxicity of available systemic drugs and great difference between their *in vitro* and *in vivo* effects (Wong *et al.*, 1997).

Mycotic keratitis is the disease caused by fungal invasion of the corneal stroma, infection is exogenous, entering through injured corneal epithelium (Kwon-Chung and Bennett, 1992).

Fungal keratitis probably arises as a result of an interaction between agent and host factors, for example; toxigenicity, invasiveness of a fungal strain by adhesion to host cell and production of enzymes that destroy defensive mechanisms of the host or attenuated immune system of host by prolonged antibiotic treatment or corticosteroid overdose after surgery (Martin *et al.*, 1995).

Mycotic keratitis is a severe problem in most of the developing countries; where as specific antifungal agents are expensive and commercially unavailable as ready compounds for topical ocular use (Al-Hussaini, 1990).

Corneal ulcer is a common disease in Upper Egypt, where 250 cases were clinically diagnosed with ulcerative keratitis within a period of 28 months by Moharram *et al.* (1999). Consequently, fungal keratitis appeared in 28% of them (70 cases out of 250), their activities increased during summer season among farmers, where several crops were harvested. Most of

isolated fungi were observed to produce extracellular enzymes and toxins; acting as offensive forces to establish the ulcer.

Corneal infections including fungal types are responsible for about 50% of corneal scarring in the developing world, which is a significant cause of blindness (Prashat *et al.*, 1999).

World Health Organization reported that about 10 millions all over the world were blind due to corneal infections, including mycotic types, in its program for prevention of blindness, stated in Global Initiative Vision by the year 2020 (Gorden, 1999).

According to predisposing factors, clinical features, and response to treatments, fungal corneal pathogens can be divided into four groups namely: filamentous fungi, yeast, yeast-like, and dimorphic fungi. Identification of pathogenic corneal fungi is performed either by microscopic stained corneal scraps or by their cultural features (O'Day, 1996).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Clinical diagnosis of corneal ulcers:

A survey was carried out on patients clinically diagnosed to have corneal ulcers of different types in the out-patient clinic and in-patient department of ophthalmology of Tanta University Hospital in the period from May 2000 to April 2002. Then patients with mycotic keratitis were assigned for more detailed studies.

Different types of corneal ulcers were clinically diagnosed and distinguished from each other on the basis of some clinical criteria, including:

1. Traumatic corneal ulcers:

- Photophobia, lacrimation and foreign body sensation.
- Punctate keratopathy in localized areas of the cornea (Hyndiuk *et al.*, 1986).

2. Bacterial corneal ulcers:

- Central keratitis associated with hypopyon and severe anterior chamber reaction.
- Deep intrastromal abscesses, commonly lead to perforation.
- Localized ulcer surrounded by nonedematous clear stroma (Pavan, 1994).

3. Viral corneal ulcers:

- Atypically, diffuse punctate plaques of swollen epithelial cells.
- Multiple scattered, thin branched, microdendritic ulcers.
- Death of stromal cells, resulting in edema, infiltration and vascularization (Shuster *et al.*, 1988).

4. Mycotic corneal ulcers:

- Initially, foreign body sensation and slow onset of increasing pain (Wilhelmus and Robinson, 1991).
- Thick area of keratitis with thick sticky hypopyon (Chander and Sharma, 1994).
- Stromal infiltrates with feathery edges and area of epithelial defect (Thomas, 1994).
- Coagulative necrosis with the loss of keratocytes and disruption of collagen lamellae due to secretion of fungal enzymes as phospholipase, collagenase and

proteases. That leads to puncture of Descemet's membrane, resulting in passage of fungi to the anterior chamber (Herbert and Michael, 1990).

For each patient, name, age, sex, occupation, residence, family crowding, water source, sewage disposal, infected eye, site of infection and history of disease were reported. Then all informations were tabulated.

Statistical analysis was carried out for all row data using SPSS software program (version 10), produced by SPSS inc. in 1999.

Culture techniques:

Samples were taken by flamed platinum spatula (or autoclaved cotton swab for soft ulcers to avoid perforation). Conjunctiva and eyelids were avoided in corneal scraping, C-streaks were made to distinguish corneal scrapings from other plate contaminants (Margo and Brinser, 1987).

Each sample was cultured on 3 Petri dishes of Sabouraud's dextrose agar medium with 0.05% chloramphenicol, incubated at 27°C for 4 to 21 days. Isolated fungi were identified, and stored at normal freezing under 4°C for further investigation.

Identification of fungi:

The following references were used for the identification of different fungal genera and species:

Moubasher (1993); Ellis (1971); Booth (1971); Raper *et al.* (1968); and Raper and Fennel (1965).

Enzyme assays:

All isolated fungi from corneal ulcers during our survey were tested for different extracellular enzyme activities as follow:

1- Collagenase assay:

Production of collagenase was induced by incubation of each fungal isolate on a collagen-dependant liquid culture (0.5 mg/ml native bovine collagen, 0.36 mM CaCl₂, and 25 mM Tris in dist. H₂O, pH= 7.5) for 1 week at 37°C in a shaking incubator. Cultures were centrifuged, supernatants (with crude enzyme) were tested for collagenase activity by the following modified procedure (Barret *et al.*, 1989):

Native bovine collagen substrate (25 mg) was incubated for 15 min. in 5 ml Tris buffer (pH=7.5) at 37°C. Reaction was started by adding 0.1 ml crude enzyme solution of each fungal isolate to one of the appropriate tubes which incubated for 5 h. at 37°C. Reaction was stopped by transferring 0.2 ml of reaction mixture into a tube with 1 ml of ninhydrin (0.25% (w/v) in acetone), heated in water bath for 20 min. Positive result of collagenase activity (collagen breakage) was detected by purple colour formed due to reaction of ninhydrin with the resultant amino acids and peptides.

2- Phospholipase assay:

The growth of 18 hrs culture of each isolate on Sabouraud's dextrose agar was harvested in 5 ml of sterile saline. This suspension (10 µL) was spot inoculated onto SDA plates supplemented with egg yolk suspension (8% v/v) and mineral salts (0.05 M CaCl₂ & 1 M NaCl). After incubation of plates at 37°C for 4 days in a humid chamber, the diameter of resultant colonies and that of precipitation zones around them were measured with a measuring scale. Phospholipase activity (Pz value) was calculated as a percentage ratio of diameter of colony to diameter of colony + precipitation zone (Price *et al.*, 1982).

3- Protease assay:

Testing of protease was performed on casein substrate, following the modified procedure of Paterson and Bridge (1994):

One gram of agar was dissolved in 60 ml of 50 mM Tris, 10 mM CaCl₂ at pH=8 in hot water bath, cooled to 65°C, 50 mg of casein substrate powder were dissolved in 40 ml of buffer (pH=8), mixed with last agar solution, heated at 90°C with stirring for 10 min. and poured in sterile plates, avoiding air bubbles, being sure that the gel thickness is uniform. A well of 1 mm diameter was punched on each plate using tip of sterilized pasteur pipette and kept in a humidified chamber. On the other hand, the growth of each isolate was harvested in 5 ml of sterile saline, 5 µL of each isolate suspension were pipetted in a well of each plate and incubated at 25°C for 16 h. Reactions was stopped by covering agar with filter papers soaked in 5% acetic acid, this could enhance contrast of the cleared zones resulting from proteolysis. Protease activity (Pz value) was calculated as a percentage ratio of diameter of colony to diameter of colony + cleared zone.

4- Urease assay:

Five ml of 10% urea solution, 5 drops of 5% Na₂ CO₃, 2 drops of phenol phthalene indicator were mixed in a test tube, and the formed pink colour of alkaline mixture was observed. Neutralization with 2% acetic acid solution was added dropwise till pink colour disappeared. Two ml of isolate fresh growth suspension were added, harvested in sterile saline, and incubated in water bath at 50°C for 15 min. Positive urease production could be detected by return of pink colour (Larone, 1995).

5- Catalase assay:

Fresh cultures of different fungal isolates were prepared (previously incubated on SDA medium at 25°C for 4 days till getting a suitable growth), then H₂O₂ solution was added onto the surface of plates for about 5 min. Positive catalase production was indicated by evolution of O₂ bubbles, resulting from decomposition of H₂O₂ (Collins and Lyne, 1984).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Seventy four patients out of 991 with corneal ulcers were clinically diagnosed with mycotic keratitis and confirmed by positive culture results for fungal growth. They were assigned for more detailed studies during 2 years of survey (May 2000 to April 2002).

a) Epidemiology of corneal ulcers:

The present survey revealed that traumatic ulcer was the most common type of corneal ulcer, and its rate was abundant at May, June-(2000), May, June-(2001), and November, December-(2001). Bacterial and viral ulcers were less common. However, the mycotic ulcers were the least common corneal ulcers (Table 1). Rate of bacterial ulcers arised at July- (2000), June-August- (2001); but the rate of viral ulcers dominated at September- (2000), September-(2001) and January- (2002). On the other hand, rate of mycotic ulcers was most common at May, June, August- (2000) and May- (2001).

The evaluation of bacterial and mycotic ulcers by ANOVA test (least significant difference) among seasons of the year (2000/2001) was significant at probability ≤ 0.05 and variation of other traumatic and viral ulcers was not significant (Table 2). On the other hand; testing of bacterial ulcers among seasons of the year (2001/2002) was significant and variation of other traumatic, viral, and mycotic ulcers was not significant during this survey. The incidence of bacterial and mycotic ulcers reached the highest rate in summer season of the first year. However, only bacterial ulcers were abundant in summer season of the second year. Additionally, the regular incidence of traumatic and viral ulcers were recorded among different seasons of the year.

Table (1): Monthly variation of traumatic, bacterial, viral, and mycotic ulcer cases during two years of survey (2000/2002):

Month	Traumatic ulcers	Bacterial ulcers	Viral ulcers	Mycotic ulcers	Total corneal ulcers
5/2000	44	8	9	13	74
6/2000	40	9	9	10	68
7/2000	23	11	5	7	46
8/2000	16	8	6	10	40
9/2000	20	7	13	4	44
10/2000	23	5	6	4	38
11/2000	36	3	4	3	46
12/2000	34	5	3	2	44
1/2001	13	7	9	3	32
2/2001	15	8	5	2	30
3/2001	27	5	4	3	39
4/2001	24	7	5	5	41
5/2001	36	6	8	3	53
6/2001	31	10	9	2	52
7/2001	19	10	4	1	34
8/2001	15	9	7	-	31
9/2001	18	6	14	1	39
10/2001	24	6	6	-	36
11/2001	38	4	4	1	47
12/2001	33	3	4	-	40
1/2002	14	8	10	-	32
2/2002	9	6	5	-	20
3/2002	22	5	3	-	30
4/2002	21	8	6	-	35
Total	595	164	158	74	991

Table (2): ANOVA test for different types of corneal ulcers during two years of survey (2000/2002):

Year	Season	Traumatic Ulcers	Bacterial ulcers	Viral ulcers	Mycotic ulcers
2000/2001	Spring	95±10	20±1	18±2	21±2
	Summer	79±7	26±2	20±2	27±1
	Autumn	79±8	15±1	23±2	11±1
	Winter	62±6	20±1	17±2	7±1
	F. value	0.509 ⁻	3.505 ⁻	0.217 ⁻	3.523 ⁻
	L.S.D.	8.9 ⁻	1.354 [*]	2.677 ⁻	2.297 [*]
2001/2002	Spring	79±8	19±1	17±1	3±1
	Summer	65±6	29±2	20±2	3±1
	Autumn	80±7	16±1	24±2	2±0
	Winter	56±5	17±1	19±1	-
	F. value	0.441 ⁻	4.591 [*]	0.227 ⁻	0.615 ⁻
	L.S.D.	8.219 ⁻	1.312 [*]	2.915 ⁻	0.85 ⁻

- : insignificant at 5% level.

* : significant at 5% level.

In the present study, fungal infection was a common reason of corneal ulcer (74 cases were recorded) which was close to the results of Moharram *et al.*(1999) who recorded 70

mycotic corneal ulcer cases within 28 months in Assiut governorate. Incidence of mycotic corneal ulcer was noticeable all over the world, where 66 cases of mycotic keratitis had been revealed in 2 years in Sri Lanka (Onawadena *et al.*, 1994), and 125 cases were recorded in about 10 years in South Florida (Rosa *et al.*, 1994).

The present survey on corneal ulcers revealed that mycotic keratitis was more common in summer and spring months, during which temperature, wind, and other environmental factors were suitable for growth and dispersion of fungi. Also many crops are harvested in these seasons, resulting in greater possibility of vegetative corneal trauma and eye contamination with fungal spores among farmers and other crop-dealers. Table (3) shows that the most common fungal species from cases of corneal ulcers during the present survey were *Aspergillus flavus* (18.9%) followed by *Mucor racemosus* (14.9%), *Aspergillus niger* (14.9%), *Penicillium lanosum* (12.2%), *Mucor fuscus* (8.1%), *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* (8.1%), *Fusarium moniliforme* (6.8%), *Mortierella horticola* (6.8%), *Sclerotium rolfsii* (4.1%), *Trimmatostroma salicis* (2.7%) and *Stachybotrys chartarum* (2.7%). These records were supported by the high prevalence of *Aspergillus* species in India (Venugopal *et al.*, 1989), Nigeria (Gugnani *et al.*, 1976), and Saudi Arabia (Khairallah *et al.*, 1992). Other fungal species were recorded with moderate incidence such as *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, *Mucor fuscus* and *Fusarium moniliforme*, and this was similar with a previous survey in Singapore (Wong *et al.*, 1996). There were other studies recording a moderate prevalence of *Fusarium* species in Egypt (Al-Hussaini, 1990), India (Panda *et al.*, 1997) and Argentina (Albrecht and Gomez, 1993).

Figure (1) represents some complications, that could be observed in clinical diagnosis of corneas infected by the different isolated fungi.

Cluster analysis for fungal isolates during the survey (2000/2002) depended on the percentage of each fungal species in the total mycotic ulcers, was carried out using SPSS software program (version 10), produced by SPSS inc. in 1999. The resultant dendrogram of the cluster analysis (Figure 2) summerizes all fungi in two groups at dissimilarity level of about 25%. A detailed study of the previous diseases and occupational history of patients could explain this differentiation and exclude the risk factors affecting the prevalence of each group of fungi among different patients suffering from mycotic keratitis. The first group contains a single fungus, namely *Aspergillus flavus*, which was more common in patients with previous ocular surgery (ex.: intra ocular lens, cataract) associated with prolonged systemic antibiotic treatment and other systemic disorders (ex.: diabetes, hypertension). The second group is subdivided at about 6% dissimilarity into two groups, one group contains *Mortierella horticola*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Trimmatostroma salicis* and *Stachybotrys chartarum*, their incidence was enhanced by heavy post operative corticosteroid doses and more common as a secondary infection after topical antibiotic treatment of bacterial lesions in cornea. The remaining group is subdivided at about 3% dissimilarity into new two subgroups, one contains *Mucor fuscus*, *Cladosporium sphaerospermum* and *Fusarium moniliforme*, recording a noticeable spread among farmers was due to exposure to organic ocular trauma during their work, dealing with plant wastes (ex.: wheat and rice straws) or harvesting of crops contaminated by infectious fungal spores. and the 2nd contains *Mucor racemosus*, *Penicillium lanosum* and *Aspergillus niger*, those were shown to be more frequent among housewives and unskilled professionals, exposed to bird wastes or dust contaminated with fungal spores, those can invade cornea easily through a metallic trauma.

Mycotic corneal ulcer was more common among people of age ranging between 40-60 years (45.9%), while it was less common among ages below and above this range during the two years of our survey (Table 4).

Table (3): Fungi isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers in the two years of survey (2000/2002):

Fungus	No.of caused ulcers	Percentage out of total mycotic ulcers
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> (Link)	14	18.9
<i>Mucor racemosus</i> (Fresenius)	11	14.9
<i>Penicillium lanosum</i> (Dierckx)	9	12.2
<i>Aspergillus niger</i> (Tieghem)	11	14.9
<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i> (Penzig)	6	8.1
<i>Mucor fuscus</i> (Bainier)	6	8.1
<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> var. <i>subglutinans</i> (Wollenweber)	5	6.8
<i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i> (Saccardo)	3	4.1
<i>Trimmatostroma salicis</i> (Corda)	2	2.7
<i>Stachybotrys chartarum</i> (Hughes)	2	2.7
<i>Mortierella horticola</i> (Linnemann)	5	6.8
Total of mycotic ulcers	74	

Table (4): Incidence of mycotic ulcers in relation to age in the two years of survey (2000/2002):

Age in years	No.of cases	% out of total cases
≤ 20	8	10.8
>20 to ≤ 40	11	14.9
>40 to ≤ 60	34	45.9
>60	21	28.4
Total of mycotic cases	74	

Regarding age and sex distribution, mycotic keratitis was more common in cases of age above 40 years. The incidence was higher in males (about 65%) than females (about 35%), that could be explained by the increased outdoor activities of males relative to females in our oriental community which expose them to risks of ocular trauma. These findings were close to those in India (Chander and Sharma, 1994). A previous study in Egypt showed a male to female ratio of 9:1 with age range >40 years (Al-Hussaini *et al.*, 1994). Moreover, the study of Moharram *et al.* (1999) revealed that fungal keratitis affected males more than females, more common in those aged >20 years up to 50 years. Also, another study reported higher incidence of mycotic keratitis in females (56%) than males (44%), that could be attributed to the increased life span and increased female outdoor activities in such occidental communities (Bennett *et al.*, 1998).

Mycotic keratitis (Table 5) was more common in males than females, in crowded families occupying rural houses than urban families, and in houses of outdoor water source and sewage disposal by conservancy than houses of indoor water supply and pipe system for sewage disposal. Also it was found that mycotic keratitis was more common among farmers, then housewives, and professionals, but less common among indoor workers. It was also more common in central cornea of left eyes and patients of prolonged antibiotic treatment than peripheral cornea, right eyes and patients without antibiotic treatments. Also it was observed that mostly it followed ocular surgery with corticosteroid treatment (lead to suppressed immunity) or ocular trauma caused by an organic matter (ex.: plant wastes) than metallic trauma or systemic diseases (ex.: diabetes, hypertension or an immune disease).

Mycotic keratitis was common and possessed higher incidence in large families with high crowding index, and rural residence of bad sanitation (sewage disposal by conservancy, and outdoor water sources). These findings were concluded also in other studies in India

(Deshapande and Koppikar, 1999), and Bangladesh (Dunlop *et al.*, 1994). Farming was the main job of mycotic keratitis patients (46%) followed by housewives (23%), and professionals (16%). This finding was confirmed by a previous study in Egypt, in which mycotic keratitis was of high incidence in farmers (64%) and housewives (20%) among many classes of patient jobs (Moharram *et al.*, 1999). These results were supported by other studies in Paraguay (Mino de Kasper *et al.*, 1991), and India (Chander and Sharma, 1994).

Mycotic keratitis was more common after organic ocular trauma (26%) and ocular surgery (30%) and less common with metallic ocular trauma (9%) and other systemic illness (15%). All these findings supported the previous results recorded in Malaysia (Sukumaran, 1991), South Florida (Jones *et al.*, 1972), and other southern parts of the United States (Kunimoto *et al.*, 1998). In Egypt, Al-Hussaini *et al.* (1994) and Rinivasan, *et al.* (1997) reported that the major risk factor of mycotic keratitis was ocular trauma of plant origin (63%) followed by metallic trauma (20%) and previous ocular surgery (12%) with prolonged antibiotic and corticosteroid treatments.

About 66% of recorded cases of mycotic keratitis were treated by antibiotics for long periods and suffering from weakened immunity. The same record was confirmed by other studies in South Florida (Rosa *et al.*, 1994), South India (Rinivasan *et al.*, 1997) and Singapore (Wong *et al.*, 1996).

Spread of viral corneal ulcers depending on sex, residence, water source, sewage disposal and family crowding was similar to that of mycotic ulcers (Table 5). However, bacterial ulcers were found to be rarely affected by residence and other house conditions of patients.

From the study of relation between spread of corneal ulcers and the habit of patient's work (Table 5), it was observed that farmers were the most common class exposed to all types of corneal ulcers. However, indoor workers were exposed to viral and bacterial ulcers more than mycotic ulcers. On the other hand, professionals and housewives were more exposed to mycotic corneal ulcers. Also, mycotic ulcers were more associated with ocular surgery, then organic ocular trauma. However, viral ulcers were more common in cases of metallic and organic ocular trauma, but not for cases of ocular surgery. On the other hand, bacterial ulcers were more spread with organic ocular trauma and cases of other systemic diseases, but very rare in cases of ocular surgery.

Farmers were the most affected patients by all three types of infectious corneal ulcers; however, indoor workers were exposed to bacterial and viral ulcers more than mycotic ulcers in cornea. This was in agreement with the results in Paraguay (Mino de Kasper *et al.*, 1991) and India (Deshapande and Koppikar, 1999). Also the relation between corneal ulcer development and other ocular or systemic diseases showed that mycotic corneal ulcers were common in patients with previous organic ocular trauma or ocular surgery. On the other hand, bacterial and viral corneal ulcers appeared after metallic ocular trauma, and not or rarely observable after ocular surgery. This supported the results recorded in Malaysia by Sukumaran (1991) and Panda *et al.* (1994).

b) Enzyme activity of fungal isolates:

The efficiency of enzyme production by different fungi isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers was noticeably variable (Figure 3) and the most efficient producers of phospholipase were *Aspergillus flavus* and *Stachybotrys chartarum* and followed by *Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium lanosum* and *Fusarium moniliforme*. However the least efficient producers were *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Mucor racemosus*. The remaining species didn't exhibit any phospholipase activity.

Test for protease activity (Figure 3) showed that *Aspergillus flavus* and *Mucor fuscus* were the most efficient producers, followed by *Penicillium lanosum* and *Trimmatostroma*

salicis. However, *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, *Sclerotium rolfsii* were the least efficient producers. The remaining species had no proteolytic activity on casein.

Urease activity was less common among the fungal isolates from corneal ulcers, while only *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Stachybotrys chartarum* and *Mortierella horticola* represented positive urease production (Table 6). On the other hand, catalase activity was more common among these isolates and the most efficient catalase producers were *Sclerotium rolfsii*, then *Aspergillus flavus*, *Mucor racemosus* and *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*. The least producers were *Penicillium lanosum*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Mucor fuscus*, *Trimmatostroma salicis* and *Mortierella horticola*. The other tested species were negative to catalase activity.

Table (5): Incidence of mycotic, bacterial and viral ulcers in relation to patient's disease, therapy history and other human life conditions in the two years of survey (2000/2002):

Risk factor	Mycotic ulcers		Percentage out of total viral	Percentage out of total bacterial ulcer cases
	No. of cases	Percentage out of total mycotic ulcer cases		
Sex frequency:				
Male	48	64.9	60	68.5
Female	26	35.1	40	31.5
Residence:				
Rural	59	79.7	80	57
Urban	15	20.3	20	43
Water source:				
Indoor	21	28.4	20	43
Outdoor	53	71.6	80	57
Sewage disposal:				
Pipes	13	17.6	16	43
Concervancy	61	82.4	84	57
Family size (crowding):				
≤ 4	20	27.1	44	31.5
> 4	54	72.9	56	68.5
Occupation:				
Farmers	34	45.9	52	54.3
Housewives	17	22.9	20	8.5
Professionals	12	16.2	8	5.7
Indoor workers	11	15.0	20	31.5
Infected eye:				
Right	33	44.6	48	60
Left	41	55.4	52	40
Site of infection:				
Central cornea	53	71.6	60	54.3
Peripheral cornea	21	28.4	40	45.7
Disease history:				
Other systemic diseases	11	15.0	16	28.5
Ocular trauma (organic)	19	25.5	24	40
Ocular trauma (metallic)	7	9.5	44	20
Ocular surgery	22	29.7	0.0	3
No obvious causes	15	20.3	16	8.5
Therapy history:				
Prolonged antibiotic	49	66.2	44	54.3
No antibiotic	25	33.8	56	45.7

Table (6): Activity of urease, and catalase enzymes produced by fungi, isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers in two years of survey (2000/2002).

Fungal isolate	Urease activity	Catalase activity	Collagenase activity
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	-ve	++	-ve
<i>Mucor racemosus</i>	-ve	++	+ve
<i>Penicillium lanosum</i>	-ve	+	-ve
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	-ve	+	+ve
<i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i>	+ve	++	+ve
<i>Mucor fuscus</i>	-ve	+	+ve
<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i> var. <i>subglutinans</i>	+ve	-ve	+ve
<i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>	+ve	+++	-ve
<i>Trimmatostroma salicis</i>	-ve	+	+ve
<i>Stachybotrys chartarum</i>	+ve	-ve	-ve
<i>Mortierella horticola</i>	+ve	+	+ve

-ve: no enzyme production, +ve: enzyme is produced.

+: low enzyme activity, ++: moderate enzyme activity.

+++: high enzyme activity.

Production of collagenase was induced by *Mucor racemosus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Cladosporium sphaerospermum*, *Mucor fuscus*, *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Trimmatostroma salicis* and *Mortierella horticola*.

Fungal growth can be established within corneal tissues by strong offensive forces such as secretion of different extracellular enzymes. The production of such enzymes (phospholipase, proteases, collagenase, urease, and catalase) by the invading fungi could lead to coagulative necrosis in cornea with loss of keratocytes and disruption of collagen lamellae (Herbert and Michael, 1990). So a part of the present work was focused on detecting the ability of different isolated keratitis fungi to produce one or more of these enzymes, which may help in the passage of fungi to the anterior chamber by destroying physical barriers, like Descemet's membrane and collagen bundles of cornea (Jones, 1980), which could be a reason of tissue damage (Kothary *et al.*, 1984). In the present work, lipolytic activity was observed for 73% of isolated keratitis fungi, and collagenase was detected in cultures of 64% of isolates; however, protease activity on casein was represented only by 55% of isolates. This was in agreement with results of a previous study on proteinase (on milk protein) and collagenase for keratitis fungi (Zhu *et al.*, 1990). Also, it was found that catalase was the most frequent enzyme, secreted by 82% of the present fungal isolates, and urease was the least frequent enzyme, secreted only by 45% of keratitis fungi. Work in progress to test various inhibitors against the studied enzymes which might be used as a therapy in order to eliminate the fungal infection or inhibit the progress of infection.

<p>Perforation of cornea, caused by <i>Aspergillus flavus</i>.</p>	<p>Corneal thinning with hypopyon, caused by <i>Mucor racemosus</i>.</p>	<p>Active fungal keratitis, caused by <i>Penicillium lanosum</i>.</p>
<p>Corneal facet, caused by <i>Aspergillus niger</i>.</p>	<p>Fungal ring abscess, caused by <i>Cladosporium sphaerospermum</i>.</p>	<p>Corneal opacity, caused by <i>Mucor fuscus</i>.</p>
<p>Corneal melting, caused by <i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>.</p>	<p>Faint corneal scar, caused by, <i>Sclerotium rolfsii</i>.</p>	<p>Vascularized corneal opacity, caused by <i>Trimmatostroma salicis</i>.</p>
<p>Corneal gutter, caused by <i>Stachybotrys chartarum</i>.</p>	<p>Endophthalmitis, caused by <i>Mortierella horticola</i>.</p>	

Fig.(1): Some representative examples for corneal complications caused by different fungi, isolated during the two years of survey.

Fig. (2): Cluster analysis for the isolated fungi from mycotic ulcers during the two years of survey (2000/2002).

Fig. (3): Activity of phospholipase, and protease enzymes produced by fungi, isolated from mycotic corneal ulcers during the two years of survey.

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دراسة على التهابات قرنية الإنسان بمستشفى الرمد بجامعة طنطا مع عناية خاصة بالمسببات الفطرية.

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تم تشخيص الإلتهاب الفطرى لقرنية العين فى ٧٤ حالة من ٩٩١ حالة مرضية بالعيادات الخاصة بقسم الرمد بمستشفيات جامعة طنطا فى الفترة من مايو ٢٠٠٠ إلى أبريل ٢٠٠٢ ، كما تم تحديد المظاهر الإكلينيكية و البيولوجية لها. وقد لفت الإنتباه عزل بعض الفطريات لأول مرة من العين مثل تريماتوستروما ساليسس، سكليروشيوم رولفسياي، ستاكيوتريس كارتارام، مورتيريللا هورتيكولا؛ بالإضافة إلى أكثر الفطريات شيوعا فى القرحة الفطرية لقرنية الإنسان مثل أسبيرجيلس فلافس، ميوكر راسيموزاس، بنيسيليوم لانوزام، أسبيرجيلس نيجر.

كما لوحظ أن القرحة الفطرية منتشرة بشكل أوسع فى قرنية الذكور عن الإناث، وفى الفلاحين، ربات المنزل، ذوى الأعمار الأكبر من الأربعين، قاطنى المنازل الريفية عن موظفى المكاتب، وقاطنى المنازل الحضرية. وتم التنبيه لأهمية حماية العين والعناية بالصحة العامة وتطوير العناية الطبية بالمرضى فى التقليل من إنتشار القرحة الفطرية بقرنية الإنسان.

أيضا تم إختبار نشاط بعض الإنزيمات مثل الكولاجينيز، الفوسفوليبيز، البروتينيز، اليورينيز، الكاتاليز للفطريات المعزولة.